

Technische Universität Berlin

INSTITUT FÜR ENERGIETECHNIK

Website: www.iet.tu-berlin.de

PDF release A

The energy-services supply systems (ESSS) common model initiative

Robbie Morrison <morrison@iet.tu-berlin.de>

PhD student, Institute for Energy Engineering, Technical University of Berlin, Germany

06 September 2002

Abstract

This document proposes a framework to facilitate the sharing of models between various energy-services supply systems modeling project. The material presented is intended as a starting point for discussion.

1. Overview

Context: A number of generic energy-services supply systems (ESSS) modeling environments are currently under development. Moreover, interest in this type of modeling looks set to continue.

Rationale: There are potential benefits to be gained if some commonality of model specification can be established between related modeling projects. One useful outcome would be the ability to share test models and compare output — with obvious advantages for software quality assurance.

Candidate projects: The focus here is on a particular form of modeling environment — one which embeds optimization functionality, offers high temporal and structural resolution, and

WORK IN PROGRESS

Covering document
ESSS common model initiative

B-1
06 Sep 02

possibly sets certain thermodynamic intensities internally (for instance, heat transfer media temperatures). These modeling environments provide a more abstracted view of ESSS than would normally be the case with engineering modeling (using `GateCycle`, for example) and greater structural detail when compared with traditional optimization-based policy-support modeling (under `MARKAL`, say). These environments replace detailed engineering simulations with reduced-form process/flow descriptions and substitute system control protocols with unit commitment policies based on minimum cost flow. In terms of temporal resolution, a nominal time discretization of one hour is typical. Furthermore, the modeling environments under consideration are often applied to support cost-effective CO₂ reduction and thereby fall under the general header of energy–emissions modeling (EEM).

Title: The term 'ESSS common model initiative' is proposed for this exercise — unless a better suggestion is forthcoming.

Components: The ESSS common model initiative could comprise the following components:

- a **collection of test data-sets** — particularly useful for software validation
- a **common data-model** — with an emphasis on high-level structure
- a **common data format** — marked up in XML
- a **sample data-set** — based on a simplified version of the *deeco* tutorial problem ¹
- a **common results interpretation protocol** — advisory only
- a **common statement of data-modeling assumptions and rules**
- a **common glossary** — which allows for synonyms

Supporting languages: The following languages have been selected to support this initiative:

- **UML** — unified modeling language — to articulate the underlying data-model
- **XML** — extensible markup language — for data interchange and persistent storage

High-level compliance: It is not intended that the proposed common data-model would be directly applicable to a particular modeling environment. Nonetheless, it is desirable that data-sets from participating modeling projects be broadly compatible with the common data-model, particularly in terms of high level structure.

Data-model scope issues: The proposed data-model places technology module code within the program domain (compile-time inclusion) rather than within the data-set proper (run-time interpretation). This represents the most conservative approach in terms of software design. In any event, the details of required technologies should be fully described and appended to the data-set.

Integration of specification and results: The proposed data-model combines model specification (input) and model results (output) data in the one structure. This will facilitate automated report generation and should assist data management and archive control.

Model data validity: Because XML has been selected to mark up data-sets, the option of writing an XML Schema to check the validity of model specifications and model results presents itself.

¹ *deeco* is one projects involved, see: www.iet.tu-berlin.de/deeco/tutorial.html.

Implementation dependencies: Some aspects will doubtless be difficult to harmonize across modeling projects — the treatment of thermal storage and heat transport are possible examples. The details of these kinds of technologies are likely to remain implementation dependent to a significant degree. This means that intentionally unrealistic test-suite technologies may be necessary in order to facilitate the wide-spread acceptance of test problems.

Forward planning: Where practicable, the data-model should be developed with potential modeling environment extensions in mind.

Version control: At this stage, data-model and data format version control is not warranted, but may become necessary as the initiative develops.

deeco-like: The proposal given here is very roughly in line with thinking about what an extended *deeco* project might look like in terms of its data-model and data format. Such convergence is not necessarily a bad idea — although the formation of agreed common model protocols will need to remain a consensus exercise.

Latest release: The latest release of this document suite should be downloadable in PDF format from: www.iet.tu-berlin.de/deeco/work-in-progress.html

2. Participating projects

The following projects form the basis for discussions at this point in time — please let me know if other projects should be included in the loop:

<i>Project</i>	<i>Institute</i>	<i>Contact</i>
TOP–Energy <i>deeco</i>	LTT, RWTH–Aachen, Germany IET, TU–Berlin, German	Eckhardt Augenstein Robbie Morrison

3. Document suite

The following documents currently make up this initiative:

<i>Role</i>	<i>Sheets</i>	<i>Language</i>	<i>Comments</i>
Data-model	D–1,2,3,4,5	UML	mostly complete
Data format	F–	XML	absent
Background	B–1	English	partially complete

4. UML and XML

Some comments about UML (unified modeling language) and XML (extensible markup language) are in order.

UML is a *modeling language* used to describe system-based processes. UML allows a given problem/solution model to be interpreted variously from the perspective of the user, the structure of the system, the potential behavior of the system, the system surroundings, the software architecture, and the deployment strategy. UML supports a well-developed notation for creating diagrams and an equally well-developed terminology.

UML is used here to articulate data-models *via* class diagrams — these diagrams capture static structure and are the appropriate choice (Microsoft `visio` was used to prepare the actual sheets).

XML is a tree-oriented data and document *markup language* which emphasizes organization based on content rather than presentation. XML is both portable and intelligible to humans. XML files can be validated against document definitions written in XML Schema and transformed to other data formats (such as comma-separated ASCII) using XSLT scripts (Matlab R13 now supports the XML (Java DOM) tree model and XSLT processing).

5. Negotiation process

At this point in time, the working style is informal.

6. Similar initiatives

It is useful to keep in touch with similar common data and/or modeling initiatives. These include:

- Modelica physical systems modeling language
- TIMES initiative from IER, University of Stuttgart, Germany
- Shared Analysis Project for the European Commission

7. Glossary

Unless the context indicates otherwise, the following definitions apply:

Term	UML	Definition
element	✓	Any UML concept.
entity		Any identified problem domain object, either concrete or conceptual, which needs to be represented in the model domain. An entity can be, variously, embodied in a class, stored as an attribute, or implied by a non-service operation.
model domain		The context for the evolving software model (and any related model) which, on completion, will be used to code the application. The model domain begins life as a somewhat vague concept at the start of a project and becomes more defined as the project develops.
problem domain		The real-world context with all its familiar complexity.
program domain		The domain in which an executing application program resides.

state	The intensive and extensive state of a given system as it is represented in either the problem domain or the program domain. State information is not limited to thermodynamic issues.
data-model	A data-model depicts data elements and their interrelationships.
data-set	The combination of input and output data specified to one or more related scenarios.

8. Abbreviations

Global

ASCII	American standard code for information interchange
DOM	XML document object model
EEM	energy–emissions modeling
OO	object-oriented
UML	unified modeling language
XML	extensible markup language
XSL	extensible stylesheet language
XSLT	XSL for transformation

Local

<i>deeco</i>	dynamic energy, emissions, and cost optimization
ESSS	energy-services supply systems
TOP–Energy	

visibility controls include:

- - indicates private
- + indicates public

public operations are also called services

Class

Named object

Anonymous object

an object does not usually appear on a class diagram, but the notation is shown for completeness

Association

Dependency

the relationships shown in this grey box represent compromises to the pure object-oriented paradigm

Aggregation

Composition

each class may exist in its own right

optional constraint information

the aggregation condition does not hold

Generalization

Abstract generalization

the superclass is never instantiated

Shape	Concept
box	class of entity
line	relationship

Relationship	Phrase
aggregation	"has a"
composition	"has a"
generalization	"is a"
association	"collaborates with"
dependency	"makes direct use of"

UML	C++
attribute	class/object data member
operation	class member function
method	object member function
generalization	inheritance
superclass	base class
subclass	derived class

UML class diagrams are used to document static (invariant) structure. UML class diagrams are one of nine diagram types within the UML family.

Notes:

1. UML supports a large number of refinements to the basic arrangements shown.

WORK IN PROGRESS

WORK IN PROGRESS

Notes:

1. This diagram concentrates on data input issues and only indicative application structure relating to this topic is shown.

IMPLIED APPLICATION SUPPORT

ACTUAL DATA-SET

WORK IN PROGRESS

Notes:

1. This diagram focuses on primary quantities, although, as noted, most zone-based reporting is necessarily derived.

House rules

Scenario focus

1. The primary focus is on the scenario, not the project.
2. There is no base-set specified from which scenarios can be developed by a process of addition or subtraction. Similarly there is not super-set specified from which scenarios can be developed by a process of subtraction.
3. In the same vein, zone and obligation information, which might better reside at the project level, has been placed within the scenario specification.

Costs

4. Cost can be represented by either sink flows or calculated directly — this latter strategy is adopted here.

Redundancy

5. Some level of redundancy remains in the scenario specification. Hence the data-set does not comply with accepted relational database normalization standards — although this should not present a problem because any such discrepancies can be readily detected when forming the diagraph object.

Multiple networks

6. Multiple network operators are not supported in this scheme.

WORK IN PROGRESS

House rules
ESSS common model initiative

D-5
06 Sep 02